

D7.1

Brand identity and guidelines

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EU	European Union

Executive Summary

This deliverable has been developed to present the brand identity and guidelines of the PoDIUM project, including the logo, typography, colours, and visual elements to be used in all communication and dissemination materials and activities of the project, among the consortium and with external stakeholders.

This document explains the brand rationale and describes the graphic guidelines to be followed by the consortium, including the correct use of the logo, the project's colours, the typeface to use, as well as the different templates that have been developed. This is important to ensure a strong visual identity for PoDIUM and that the PoDIUM brand is used consistently and coherently by the consortium, which will maximise the impact of the project's communication.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of Deliverable D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines* is to present the brand identity and set out the correct guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand to ensure its consistent representation in all communication and dissemination materials and activities of the project by the consortium. This document describes the logo, typography, and various visual elements to be used in internal documents and promotional materials. The different PowerPoint and Word templates that have been created for the communication and dissemination activities of all consortium partners are also presented in this document.

This document is complementary to Deliverable D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan* and Deliverable D7.3 *Communication tools*. Deliverable D7.2 will explain in greater detail the communication strategy of PoDIUM, presenting the target audience, stakeholders, dissemination channels, communication tools, and promotional materials that will be produced for the project. Deliverable D7.3 will describe the different communication tools developed as part of the project, including social media channels and the project's website, and printed material that will be created such as a leaflet and a roll-up banner.

1.2. Intended audience

This is a public document. The document will be available on the PoDIUM website. For the consortium, this document is intended to act as a guide on the correct use of the project's brand.

2. PoDIUM brand

2.1. PoDIUM graphic identity and guidelines

The guidelines describe the rationale and correct use of the PoDIUM brand and its graphic identity. The brand identity includes the logo and its different elements and variations, the brand colours and the typography to be used.

2.1.1. Brand rationale

The PoDIUM logo is a strong visual representation of the vision of the PoDIUM project. The different graphic elements that make up the logo represents both the digital and physical part of the infrastructure. The element above the “o” symbolises the multi-connectivity approach of the project, while the “U” depicts a road, i.e. the physical part of the infrastructure. The points below the “U” and the “M”, representing the wheels of a car, further emphasise the on-road elements.

The PoDIUM logo uses a simple, modern typography that looks clean and professional. It uses bold purple colours to make it stand out and be easily recognisable. To ensure consistency, the name of the project, PoDIUM, should always be spelled with all capital letters, except for the “o”, which should be written in lower case.

Figure 1: PoDIUM logo

2.1.2. Master logo

The PoDIUM master logo must always appear fully intact and must not be altered or distorted in any way. The guidelines set out in this document on the correct use of the logo must always be followed. All elements of the logo must be visible, with no alteration in proportion or position.

- **Colours of the logo**

The PoDIUM master logo is made up of dark grey, a darker and lighter shade of purple, and blue. The full-colour logo should always be used when the logo appears on a white background. If the logo appears on a dark background, the white version of the logo should be used. In case the logo needs to be reproduced in black and white, the greyscale logo or black logo should be used.

The colour codes of the master logo are the following:

- Dark grey: HEX #272e40; RGB: 39 | 46 | 64; CMYK: 87 | 74 | 47 | 53
- Darker shade of purple: HEX # 451683; RGB: 69 | 22 | 131; CMYK: 92 | 100 | 7 | 2
- Lighter shade of purple: HEX # 8E54E9; RGB: 142 | 84 | 233; CMYK: 69 | 72 | 0 | 0
- Blue: HEX # 4776E6; RGB: 71 | 118 | 230; CMYK: 76 | 55 | 0 | 0

Figure 2: PoDIUM logo colours

Figure 3: PoDIUM greyscale logo

Figure 4: PoDIUM black and white logo

- **Minimal graphic elements of the logo**

The graphic element above the “o” of the PoDIUM logo can also be used on its own where appropriate to represent the project. It can be used in various communication materials to further consolidate the PoDIUM brand and make the project visible and recognisable.

Figure 5: Minimal graphic elements of the PoDIUM logo

- Spacing of the logo

The logo must always be surrounded by clear space to ensure its visibility. This clear space corresponds to the height of the letters and must always be free of any kind of other graphic elements. The logo must not appear at the extreme edge of a page.

Figure 6: Spacing around the PoDIUM logo

- Incorrect use of the logo

The PoDIUM logo must not be distorted or stretched in any way and its integrity must be respected. All elements that make up the logo must always appear as designed without any alteration and their proportion and position relative to each other must be respected. The colours of the logo and its typography cannot be altered in any way. The logo must always remain easy to read if used on a coloured background.

Figure 7: Examples of misuses of the PoDIUM logo

2.1.3. Typography

- Marketing and promotional materials

The Roboto typeface should be used for any marketing and promotional materials. This includes posters, roll-up banners, leaflets, the project’s website and other external or promotional printed materials.

Roboto Light	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,:~?!
Roboto Regular	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,:~?!
Roboto Bold	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,:~?!
Roboto Black	ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,:~?!

H1 – Roboto Black

H2 – Roboto Bold

H3 – Roboto Medium

H4 – Roboto Medium

Body text – Roboto Regular

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Figure 8: Primary typeface for marketing and promotional materials

- Documents and internal communications

The Calibri typeface should be used for all working documents made for internal use within the consortium, such as PowerPoint presentations and Word documents, and for all official documents.

<p>Calibri Light</p> <p>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,;_~?! </p>	<p>Body text</p> <p>HEX: #272e40 RGB: 39 46 64 CMYK: 87 74 47 53</p>
<p>Calibri Regular</p> <p>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,;_~?! </p>	<p>Headline</p> <p>HEX: #451683 RGB: 69 22 131 CMYK: 92 100 7 2</p>
<p>Calibri Bold</p> <p>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,;_~?! </p>	<p>Headline</p> <p>HEX: #8E54E9 RGB: 142 84 233 CMYK: 69 72 0 0</p>
<p>Calibri Bold Italic</p> <p>ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890.,;_~?! </p>	<p>Headline</p> <p>HEX: #4776E6 RGB: 71 118 230 CMYK: 76 55 0 0</p>

Figure 9: Secondary typeface for internal and official communications

2.2. Templates

2.2.1. PowerPoint Template

A Microsoft PowerPoint presentation template has been developed. The template is in line with the PoDIUM brand identity and guidelines. It comprises a title slide, slides with text, bullet points, tables and figures, and a closing slide acknowledging EU funding.

Figure 10: PowerPoint template

2.2.2. Other templates (deliverables, meeting agenda and minutes)

Microsoft Word templates have been developed, in keeping with the PoDIUM visual identity. Templates for deliverables and for meeting agenda and minutes are available.

Figure 11: Word deliverable template

Figure 12: Word meeting agenda template

Figure 13: Word meeting minutes template

2.3. Acknowledgment of EU funds

The PoDIUM project is co-funded by the European Union. According to Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, all communication and dissemination activities and publication materials must explicitly acknowledge receipt of EU funding through the display of the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate) “Co-funded by the European Union”. The European emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands, or text. No other visual identity or logo may be used to acknowledge EU support.

Figure 14: EU funding statement (horizontal and vertical)

The correct use of the EU emblem and funding statement is available at the following link:
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

3. Summary

This deliverable D7.1 is complementary to Deliverable D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan* and Deliverable D7.3 *Communication tools*. The purpose of this document is to describe the PoDIUM project's brand identity and guidelines, explain the rationale of the logo, colours, and typeface, and detail the correct use of the project's visual identity.

All consortium partners should follow the guidelines detailed in this deliverable to ensure the consistent use of the PoDIUM brand to make it easily recognisable. This is important for the coherence of the dissemination activities of the project and to ensure maximum impact of the project's communications goals.

Consortium partners can find the different elements that make up the PoDIUM brand identity, including the logo files, guidelines, and templates through the project's [Redmine](#).